

IMPACT-BASED ASSESSMENT OF THE TRANSLATIONAL RESEARCH IN THE ITALIAN RESEARCH HOSPITALS

KICK-OFF MEETING REPORT

14 March 2025

Milano, Corso Europa 15 (Spaces San Babila)

and on Zoom platform

Associazione Ricercatori in Sanità – Italia (ARSI)

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Funded by
the European Union

Evento di kick-off del progetto

**“IMPACT-BASED ASSESSMENT OF THE TRANSLATIONAL RESEARCH
IN THE ITALIAN RESEARCH HOSPITALS”**

finanziato dall'Unione Europea

Il progetto, focalizzato sugli **Istituti di Ricovero e Cura a Carattere Scientifico (IRCCS)**, propone di fornire ai **ricercatori** strumenti concreti per dimostrare l'impatto del proprio lavoro nel mondo reale e discutere coi **decisori** di un framework per analizzare i benefici della ricerca sanitaria oltre le pubblicazioni scientifiche, secondo il Translational Science Benefit Model (TSBM)

14 MARZO 2025 h. 14 | MILANO

Spaces San Babila, Corso Europa 15, 7° Piano, Sala M3

Modalità ibrida su piattaforma Zoom

- 14:00 - 14:10** **Benvenuto dell'associazione ARSI**
Dott.ssa Francesca Colciaghi, Vicepresidente ARSI
- 14:10 - 14:25** **CoARA, le iniziative in Italia**
Dott.ssa Francesca Di Donato, Co-chair Chapter Italiano CoARA
- 14:25 - 14:45** **Presentazione progetto sull'impatto nel mondo reale della ricerca sanitaria traslazionale IRCCS**
Ing. Valeria Elisa Contarino, Presidente ARSI
- 14:45 - 15:45** **Valorizzare l'impatto della ricerca sanitaria traslazionale IRCCS: stato dell'arte, opportunità e strategie**
Discussione aperta
- 15:45 - 16:00** **Chiusura lavori**

Iscriviti qui:

<https://forms.gle/aRzLV5ttEAExyFLy6>

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<p>Registrations: 151</p> <p>On-site: 42</p> <p>Remote: 109</p>	<p>Participants: 86</p> <p>On-site: 32</p> <p>Remote: 54</p>
<p>WELCOME</p> <p>2:00-2:10 pm</p>	<p>The meeting starts at 2:00 PM with a welcome from the Vice-President of the Italian Association of Healthcare Researchers (ARSI), who thanks the colleagues attending in person or remotely from all over Italy, the representative of the Italian chapter of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) connected remotely, those from the Bibliosan Group (the Italian network of biomedical research libraries) attending in person, and the Scientific Directors of the Istituti di Ricovero e Cura a Carattere Scientifico (IRCCS) attending in person.</p> <p>The President of ARSI briefly introduces the Association, its foundation in 2017, its organizational structure, the main past activities, and the ongoing initiatives.</p>
<p>COARA Italia</p> <p>2:10-2:25 pm</p>	<p>The Co-chair of the Italian Chapter of CoARA presents the international CoARA initiative, the Italian CoARA Chapter, and the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA). In particular, the 10 commitments are outlined: 4 with specific commitments and 6 general commitments. The following key points are highlighted:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment should not rely on a single outcome, thus promoting diversity in outputs and processes; • The need to include qualitative evaluation criteria; • The importance of abandoning the inappropriate use of Journal Impact Factor and H-index; • The recommendation to avoid the use of rankings. <p>The ARRA foresees a role for open science, establishes general principles for research assessment (including ethics and integrity), and promotes transparent processes and methodologies.</p>

	<p>CoARA is structured into 13 thematic working groups, participation is voluntary, and organizations can join one or more groups. There are currently 16 national chapters, with the Italian chapter being one of the first, established in September 2023.</p> <p>Member institutions are required to submit an action plan within one year of joining, which must include a roadmap for the following five years.</p> <p>The initiative currently includes 68 Italian institutions, with 55 participating in the national chapter and 20 action plans already published.</p> <p>The main objectives of the Italian chapter are to promote mutual learning, sharing, good practices, and to raise awareness within the national research community.</p> <p>Three Work Packages (WPs) were planned: the translation of the ARRA agreement from English into Italian, the creation of specific working groups (with a focus on recruiting young researchers), and the collaboration with the other national chapters.</p> <p>An invitation is extended to join the national chapter in order to participate in upcoming meetings and activities.</p>
<p>PROJECT PRESENTATION 2:25-2:45 pm</p>	<p>The coordinator presents the project entitled “Impact-Based Assessment of Translational Research in the Italian Research Hospitals.”</p> <p>This is a pilot institutional project funded by the European Union within the first call of the CoARA Boost Cascade Funding. It mainly addresses points 2 and 3 of the ARRA, namely:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (1) complementing mainly bibliometric quantitative indicators with qualitative impact assessment criteria; (2) identifying alternatives to the inappropriate use of bibliometric indicators by using impact metrics. <p>The specific objectives of the project are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (1) to provide researchers with tools to demonstrate the impact of their work using the Translational Science Benefits Model (TSBM) framework;

(2) to engage decision-makers in discussions on TSBM as a framework for assessing real-world benefits of research;

(3) to co-design proposals to improve research assessment and valorisation methods based on the TSBM framework, aligned with ARRA principles.

The project rationale is to highlight the unique role of Italian Research Hospitals (IRCCS) within the broader scientific research landscape, rooted in the translational nature of their research activities.

The definition of translational research is discussed based on the study by Fort et al. (2017) *Mapping the evolving definitions of translational research*.

This defines five phases of translational research:

- Preclinical research (T0)
- Human efficacy studies (T1)
- Real-world effectiveness studies (T2)
- Implementation projects in clinical practice (T3)
- Impact studies on clinical outcomes and community health (T4)

Translational research is further analysed from a process perspective, referencing the study by Trochim et al. (2011) *Evaluating translational research: a process marker model*. Translational research is described as a continuous, bidirectional process from T0 to T4, where clinical needs drive scientific studies, which in turn aim to address those needs as they evolve through each phase.

Several barriers can hinder progression along this translational pathway, including technical challenges (e.g., incompatible databases), financial constraints (e.g., high costs or lack of resources), and career disincentives. A critical issue today stems from assessment systems that foster competition among individuals, making it difficult to maintain a collaborative or systemic vision of the entire translational research process, from initial evidence generation to real-world impact.

Most individuals are experts in only one phase of translational research, yet it remains essential to preserve an overall perspective and advance scientific evidence through multidisciplinary collaboration.

The presentation introduces the work by Luke et al. (2018) *The Translational Science Benefits Model: A New Framework for Assessing the Health and Societal Benefits of Clinical and Translational Sciences*. This identifies 30 potential real-world benefits of translational research, grouped into four domains: Clinical, Community, Economic, and Policy.

The study emphasises that the pathway towards real-world benefits is influenced by positive and negative scientific, cultural, financial, and political factors. These influences must be considered in translational research projects to maximise their real-world impact.

What tools can be used to manage projects with a focus on real-world benefits? In 2023, the first web version of the TSBM toolkit was released, developed based on the framework by Luke et al.

The toolkit includes nine tools:

- Four tools for project planning
- One for project monitoring
- Four for demonstrating and disseminating results

Within the CoARA project, basic training is planned for two planning tools and one demonstration tool:

- The first is the Roadmap to Impact, a one-page canvas summarising all project aspects on an A4 sheet.
- The second is the Benefit 2x2, a matrix tool that organises the 30 real-world benefits under four domains (Clinical, Community, Economic, Policy), allowing users to estimate timelines and confidence levels. This supports clear prioritisation and decision-making within the project.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The third is the Product Navigator, designed to help identify the most suitable communication product based on objectives and target audiences. <p>The project is open to researchers, research support staff, and clinicians working within the IRCCS network. It includes both basic training and practical application to ongoing research projects. Eligible projects can be at the planning stage, underway, or completed, as the TSBM tools support not only planning but also the identification of new opportunities or advancement along the translational pathway.</p> <p>Participants will be asked to complete a final survey and share their completed Benefit 2x2 after applying the TSBM to their project.</p> <p>The project work plan covers the period from January to December 2025.</p>
<p>DISCUSSION AND CLOSING REMARKS 2:45-4:00 pm</p>	<p>A representative from the Grant Office of an IRCCS research hospital asks for clarification on how the presented project intersects with ARRA. It is explained that the project mainly addresses points 2 and 3 of ARRA.</p> <p>A Scientific Director of an IRCCS research hospital requests further details regarding the expectations placed on institutions and the applicability of the tools for evaluation purposes. It is clarified that the proposed tool complements quantitative assessments by introducing markers within the translational research process to monitor progress across translational phases.</p> <p>A member of the ARSI board links the discussion to the CoARA framework, which foresees that a cultural shift is needed before new markers can be implemented alongside quantitative metrics. The project aims to foster this cultural change through the proposed tools.</p> <p>The Scientific Director enquires further about the Benefit 2x2 tool, specifically regarding the reliability of responses in terms of confidence and timing, whether the tool should be filled individually or collectively by</p>

	<p>the research group, whether it is standardised, and what potential biases may exist.</p> <p>A board member explains that the toolkit is designed to support the generation of answers through the prior use of complementary tools, providing the necessary background and reasoning. The purpose is to shift the perspective towards real-world benefits.</p> <p>Another participant highlights that the Benefit 2x2 tool supports risk-based planning and that the toolkit should involve the entire project team, including all professional roles involved.</p> <p>A Scientific Director from another IRCCS hospital raises the question of whether a questionnaire is planned to limit the number of IRCCS participating. It is explained that the level of interest expressed will naturally influence the number of institutions involved, regardless of their current project development stage. It is proposed to collect suggestions to improve the questionnaire before its dissemination.</p> <p>Remotely, a colleague from an IRCCS in Rome asks whether the project is open only to researchers or also to research support staff. It is confirmed that the project is open to all IRCCS personnel involved in research activities.</p> <p>A representative of the Bibliosan network comments on the use of bibliometric indicators, noting that while they provide an immediate number, there is a need to transition from a competitive system to a collaborative one based on sharing. He cites a 2018 study showing increased citation rates following new university teaching criteria. He supports a data management approach aimed at sharing data and verifying publications.</p> <p>One of the Scientific Directors stresses that the evaluation system, including metrics like H-index, is often distorted by factors such as career</p>
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stage and requires reform. Real-world impact is perceived differently across locations due to cultural and contextual factors.

The Bibliosan representative highlights that those managing research systems must consider complexity beyond individual evaluation. He notes that approximately one million euros per year is spent on bibliometric databases and that such indicators are used in evaluating both institutions and individual researchers.

It is reiterated that institutional Impact Factors (IF) are meaningless, and this also applies to the evaluation of individual researchers. The limitations of bibliometric indicators are well known.

One of the Scientific Directors references Yale's evaluation practices, which consider publications in top-tier journals and patents, questioning the real impact of such measures. He proposes stratifying institutions based on their profiles (e.g., preclinical, clinical, rehabilitation) to allow for comparable evaluation metrics. He supports applying the toolkit to test for biases across project stages and separating past projects from future ones.

Another Scientific Director suggests selecting projects based on research area and topic.

It is clarified that the project's goal is to start from the TSBM framework to co-create a shared tool for researchers and decision-makers, noting that strict project selection or stratification may not align with the pilot project's objectives.

The toolkit is encouraged to be tested on the presented project itself.

Questions are raised regarding the target users of the toolkit—whether individuals or research groups—and how participant seniority or expertise may affect tool application.

	<p>A researcher from another IRCCS hospital mentions using canvas tools for business planning and stresses the importance of communication, particularly for rare disease research, advocating for both stratification and patient advocacy efforts.</p> <p>The importance of communication and direct engagement with patients and associations is widely supported.</p> <p>It is suggested that a survey be conducted after the toolkit's application to gather feedback.</p> <p>In the chat, it is reiterated that ARRA point 2 specifically promotes integrating quantitative with qualitative indicators.</p> <p>A colleague from an IRCCS hospital in Rome highlights that this is just the initial phase focused on creating and analysing preliminary data.</p> <p>A participant questions the adaptability of the tool and whether it could eventually become mandatory for participation in competitive funding calls.</p> <p>The Bibliosan representative mentions data management practices (e.g., CC0 licensing, data sharing) where data should be made available prior to publication, formatted for both human and machine reuse.</p> <p>The public kick-off event concludes at 16:05.</p>
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